

LINGUISTIC AND FOREIGN STUDIES ELEMENTS AS THE BASIS OF THE COMMUNICATIVE ORIENTATION OF TEACHING RUSSIAN IN AZERBAIJANI UNIVERSITIES

Gezalova N.

PhD in Philology, Associate Professor, Azerbaijan University of Languages

Abstract

This article is devoted to various linguistic and cultural elements, the use of which, on the one hand, is aimed at increasing the level of students' knowledge in the field of culture of other countries, Russia in the first place. On the other hand, this approach saturates Russian language lessons with the above-mentioned material, teaching students to study not only Russian history and culture, but also Russia. New information in this direction does not contradict the requirements of the latest curriculum released by the Ministry of Education of Azerbaijan in 2020. The points set out in it record the state of the study of the Russian language in the universities of the republic in the modern period. In addition, the introduction of various linguistic and foreign studies elements into lesson plans (lectures and seminars) has as their ultimate goal the active introduction of the basics of communication, more precisely, communicative competence, into the teaching process of Russian as a foreign language.

If we strictly adhere to terminology, then it is understood as such a generalized personality trait, which includes the application of communicative abilities in the practice of learning. It is a way of acquiring knowledge and skills in a second language. But in our case, we are primarily referring to the ability of foreign students to engage in conversation in a non-native language. This includes the correct pronunciation, the construction of phrases in Russian, and, of course, the constant replenishment of the vocabulary with the help of a teacher. Moreover, it is also an opportunity for students to adapt in a certain way to various situations of a communicative nature. These skills also imply knowledge of the culture of the country of the language being studied, including even some social aspects.

In this way, students gain broad access to communication in a second (Russian) language with both their peers and teachers. Dialogic speech is developing as a faithful and reliable companion for accelerated and competent mastery of all sections of Russian linguistics. The work also highlights that leading Azerbaijani scientists most often follow the path laid out by prominent Russian methodist theorists. In this, the author of the article sees neither a violation of the rights and opportunities of Russian national cadres, nor an obstacle to learning the Russian language in general, because information on regional studies and Russian studies becomes the main help.

Keywords: Russian as a foreign language; Azerbaijani-speaking audience; cultural studies; regional studies; Russian studies; history; literature.

At the present stage, great changes are taking place in Azerbaijan, affecting various spheres of human life. This also applies to the field of education in the republic. The policy documents attach great importance to this area. It is characteristic that along with the state language, considerable attention is paid to the Russian language. It is unconditionally recognized by both scientists of various profiles and citizens of Azerbaijan that the Russian language is now a means of interethnic communication in the vast territory of the former post-Soviet space. The reforms of the education system in the 21st century in this republic are purposefully focused on the comprehensive development and democratization of its internal structures.

The article is based on a comparative typological method that allowed comparing some methodological techniques in the practice of teaching Russian to Azerbaijani students with a detailed explanation of the linguistic and foreign studies material.

Taking into account the above, it seems to us that there are at least three significant circumstances that should definitely be paid special attention to. First of all, even in the capital, the number of national university sectors significantly exceeds the Russian ones. We are not talking about the regions of Azerbaijan where it is extremely small. Despite the relative regularity of this phenomenon in national language policy, it negatively affects the teaching methods of the Russian lan-

guage. It seems that for native speakers of the Azerbaijani language, students are focused on mastering a certain amount of knowledge, skills and abilities in a non-native language.

But in a number of philological faculties of humanitarian universities, this process is progressing with difficulty; as a rule, the obstacle was the home language environment, where the Russian language dominates in rare cases. Secondly, the implementation of this requirement in relation to the modern university conditions in Azerbaijan involves a massive improvement of the current teaching methodology, the development of new approaches to both the selection of educational content and the ways of its presentation.

President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev and First Vice President Mehriban Aliyeva have repeatedly spoken in defense of the Russian language at various forums, conferences and meetings. Meanwhile, thirdly, we regret to state that the hours allotted for teaching Russian Philology to students in Azerbaijan are inexorably decreasing.

By the beginning of the third decade, this had become noticeable. However, despite the depressing fact related to the distribution of the workload in this subject in Azerbaijani universities, a number of methodological techniques in the process of teaching Russian are becoming more diverse. This also applies to the use of linguistic and foreign studies elements in higher education institutions of the republic, Russian studies, which

are the basis of a communicative orientation. The obvious disregard for them reduces the level of mastery of Russian by foreign-speaking students. So there is no doubt that these elements should be actively included. The purpose of this article is to briefly show their use in RAF classes at universities in Azerbaijan.

First of all, we emphasize that the teaching of any subject should be based on general didactic and particular pedagogical principles. The Russian language is no exception for foreigners, or rather, Azerbaijani students. The observance of these principles, enriched by linguistic and regional studies, forms the basis for building the entire education system. For example, the pedagogical principle of purposefulness in teaching the Russian language should not be discounted. The presentation of material from one section of Russian linguistics should prepare students for the development of a subsequent section on curricula or manuals. It is also accompanied by the principle of systematicity and consistency in the transfer of knowledge. The principle of scientific content is necessarily consistent with the tasks of an educational nature. The principle of accessibility is combined with the physiological, age and individual characteristics of students' development. The above is carried out in close connection with the principles of activity and consciousness.

It is not difficult to imagine that these principles of the pedagogical process in universities not only do not contradict the introduction of various linguistic and cultural elements in the classroom, but, on the contrary, they help it. So, from the total number of these principles developed by scientists in the field of interest to us, it is necessary to select only those that are related to the specifics of a particular subject, with the conditions and objectives of teaching a foreign language. The linguistic and cultural orientation of the construction of the Russian language course in the Azerbaijani audience as a subject of the future specialty of students presupposes the observance of the following linguistic and didactic features:

1. Specifying the tasks of teaching the Russian language at each stage of the lesson.
2. Scientific approach to the explanation of lexical and grammatical phenomena of the Russian language.
3. Clarity of presentation of educational linguistic and foreign studies material in groups of students who graduated from school in the Azerbaijani language.
4. A certain novelty (compared to the school) of the information offered by university teachers, which makes it possible to actively support students' interest in Russian language classes.
5. The interrelation and interdependence of a conglomerate of disciplines, primarily subjects such as history, literature, language, philosophy, psychology (or, more precisely, psycholinguistics).
6. Relying on the mental activity of students, identifying the level of their intellectual abilities on the well-known IQ scale.

Now let us take a closer look at some of the listed features that express the essence of linguistic and cultural features in the Russian text.

Thus, based on the opinion of authoritative Russian scientists such as E. N. Baryshnikova, M. D.

Bashin, V. S. Bezrukova, V. I. Belozertsev [1; 2; 3; 4] and some others, on the views of leading Azerbaijani theoreticians and methodologists, we can conclude that practical Russian language classes at the philological faculties of the republic's humanities universities should first and foremost have a communicative focus. It is assumed that a student, even if he graduated from an Azerbaijani school, should master practical Russian in two to two and a half years of study to such an extent that he would not be hindered by acts of communication with Russian-speaking interlocutors.

This is no easy task. It can only be successfully accomplished if students in their first year of study have a solid academic foundation. Therefore, most practical Russian language programs in Azerbaijan, especially in recent years, are built specifically on expanding interactions in a Russian-speaking environment - that is, on a communicative foundation. The communicative focus of the program lies in the study of language as a specific human activity involving speaking, listening, writing, and reading. The widespread use of professions such as translator, journalist, editor, and proof-reader in modern society has generated interest in the study of Russian in virtually all humanities faculties. Accordingly, language training in these professions should be provided. And since "contact with Russian dialogue partners requires foreign students to understand the fundamental cultural realities of Russian life, specialized training in intercultural communication is necessary when studying Russian as a second language" [5, p. 47].

Most modern methodologists, regarding the question of the connection between the culture of the people of the language being studied and the methodology of its teaching, consider it necessary to focus mainly on the culture of communication and behavior. For example, in one of G. V. Elizarova's studies on the problem of interest to us, such discrete speech acts as complaint, request for a favor, invitation, lie, disapproval, apology are considered in detail within the framework of Russian culture [6, pp. 94-114]. She symptomatically subordinates these speech acts to attribution processes, which in turn include various kinds of speech behavior patterns, stereotypes, prejudices, generalizations. But at the same time, Elizarova subordinates these stereotypes to the principles of cognition and consideration of cultural universals. But, unfortunately, she never mentions the importance of familiarizing foreign students with the history and cultural artifacts of the country of the native speaker of the language being studied. And without these components, the degree of communication in the student audience when learning Russian with a linguistic and foreign component is clearly decreasing.

Such a methodological technique as constructing a problematic situation in universities can be of great help to Azerbaijani students. By it, modern methodologists and practical teachers generally understand the need to solve the task by the students themselves. However, a problematic situation is a very broad concept; it can be formulated in almost any lesson, and not only in subjects of the humanities, but also in the technical cycle. In line with our chosen topic of the article, it is im-

portant to point out the possible enrichment of the problematic situation with linguistic and foreign elements [1]. We are convinced that this kind of lesson will be interesting, lively, and more beneficial for foreign students.

What's most interesting about this pedagogical process, in our view, is that posing a problematic situation allows for significant diversification of the lesson, symptomatically complicating the teaching methods. For example, during one semester, in elective classes, students are given the opportunity to combine listening with the use of audio-visual equipment. Simply put, this means organizing screenings of feature films followed by discussions in a seminar. We recommend such Russian-Soviet films, widely known to the older generation, as "Kuban Cossacks", "Girls", and "The Tale of the Siberian Land".

What is the reason for the choice? In the first (according to our list) there are several notable episodes about the introduction of culture to the masses of villagers and small Cossack towns (the purchase of a piano by the main character), etc. In the second, there are scenes with the construction of a Cultural center for the northern regions remote from Moscow. The third one contains a lot of information from a purely regional perspective, as well as fragments about the national mentality of Siberians. In addition, there is a rich thought about the inspiration of the metropolitan musician, who gets the opportunity to write beautiful symphonies in Siberia. In all three cases, students are given a task: after watching the recommended feature films, Azerbaijani students are invited to independently find the relevant episodes, continuing the story about the culture of the Russian peoples.

Let us now turn to more modern examples. Our attention was attracted by the work of the famous Russian writer Victoria Tokareva. In a number of her short stories and novellas – "I am. You are there. He is", "The Long Day", "The House of General Kuropatkin", "Smooth Face" and others, the author invariably seeks her own angle of view on the behavior of young people in her modern society. These essays can be recommended as extracurricular reading. It is noteworthy that, in full agreement with his subjective worldview, V. Tokareva reflects the specifics of the transition moment from love to hate, from acceptance of life with all its value orientations to indifference and despair. At the same time, there are many elements of Russian culture in her works. This is most often done by referring to the institution of marriage and family. Only Tokareva's individual vision is that most young families cannot find a common language among themselves. Literally, they are mired not only in domestic worries, but also in frequent insults, family scandals and unfounded accusations. Domestic quarrels and all sorts of minor squabbles do not allow us to "hear" each other. One can agree or disagree with this position, but one cannot deny the fact that this approach is the writer's credo regarding the culture of behavior in some young families. It is not for nothing that critics have dubbed most of her works as an example of "everyday realism".

Students in the humanities can gain essential knowledge about the culture of the target language by

reading relevant texts, which will serve as the basis for language teaching. The selection of such texts requires interdisciplinary connections and close collaboration between the departments of each humanities faculty. The concept of "interdisciplinary connections" can, to a certain extent, be considered one of the fundamental principles that ensures the communicative focus of language learning. When selecting texts for reading, specific objectives for implementing interdisciplinary connections should be identified. For example, the goal should be to develop the ability to use words from specific thematic groups. If possible, when reading and analyzing Russian texts on Russian history or literary works by Russian writers, comparisons can be made between Russia and Azerbaijan, and between Russian and Azerbaijani-or, more broadly, Eastern-literature.ing Russian texts on the history of Russia or literary texts created by Russian writers.

What exactly and objectively will this lead to? Firstly, based on such new information, students will try to independently build the most effective communication strategy. Moreover, both among peers and along the line: student – teacher. Secondly, the knowledge gained in our chosen way will help them to analyze some linguistic and cultural aspects more deeply. That is, to recognize the traits, signs, and behaviors of people of another nationality within a foreign-language culture.

The principle of relying on the mental activity of students finds its realization in various types of educational activities, in those tasks that are directly offered for execution. Being aware that not all information about Russia of a linguistic and foreign nature can be included in curricula or manuals, it is advisable for teachers to prepare a list of texts about the life of Russians in advance and invite students to speak with them publicly not only in the classes themselves, but also as additional extracurricular reading. Since students will encounter vocabulary related to history, literature, and possibly painting and other forms of art when reading such texts, they should create a thesaurus of lexical units of linguistic and cultural studies with the help of teachers. In order to implement interdisciplinary historical and literary relations and obtain this kind of information on the basis of texts selected by the teacher, students master various types of reading. At the initial stage of learning, a type of reading is used, which some Russian methodologists call "prepared" (Y. E. Prokhorov), for others - "analytical" (V. P. Furmanova). The bottom line is that in the process of this reading, students must: A) Develop a technique for fast, correct reading; B). To learn to understand what is being read better by receiving explanations from a teacher or using a dictionary about incomprehensible (difficult to pronounce) words or expressions [7, p. 128].

It is well known that, by the nature of the activity, there are educational, educational (learning), search, selective, and viewing readings. Highlighting each of them with a comment for our article would be superfluous. But these types of reading, in accordance with our "scenario", correspond to certain linguistic and cultural elements. In this case, the essence of the matter lies in the fact that the types of reading listed and already

firmly established in the methodological literature, in principle, do not cover all of them to the maximum extent. But given the presence of this component in them, they are, at our discretion, quite sufficient for practical work on learning Russian for Azerbaijani students. Much of their reading of relevant texts depends on the reproductive experience of teachers, and more specifically, on the ability to extract information from leading questions. We are convinced that with the right approach, it is possible to involve the national audience in various cultural projects that meet the knowledge of certain sections of Russian linguistics.

However, this is sometimes not achieved in an easy way. Let us explain. Since the topics of regional studies and especially Russian studies are very extensive, the text offered for reading is usually of different origin. For example, it can be created by the author of a training manual. On the one hand, at the request of the Ministry of Education of Azerbaijan, the compiler is obliged to take into account both the content and linguistic content of the text. On the other hand, textbooks sometimes include text taken from humorous literature or the “yellow press”. Such a text, of course, is far from scientific. Even if it contains some regional information, it is not advisable to analyze it in the classroom. As a last resort, this kind of text is undoubtedly subject to drastic revision. Meanwhile, it is still necessary to preserve the basic information, because it most often turns out to be adapted to the lexico-grammatical and speech tasks of a particular lesson. Even if the text on regional studies or Russian studies is taken from fiction, then, for ethical reasons, only certain abbreviations are allowed.

Above, we wrote about the lack of an urgent need to list the main functions of different types of reading. But one of them, in our opinion, needs to be mentioned in particular. It is about educational reading, in which a close connection is established between understanding, perception and memorization of texts. At the same time, memorization refers to information extracted from texts and assimilated. If the read text is meaningful and understood, then it is easy to remember. To do this, according to E. I. Rogov, “in the process of reading and when preparing a text for reading in the audience, it can be structured” [8, p. 96].

Structuring refers to the division of a text into separate semantic parts. From a purely psychological point of view, the structuring of an educational text often occurs for each reader individually, regardless of its author's division into paragraphs or parts. This is due to the different preparation of each reader for the perception of the text. In the process of structuring, each part read by students is subjected to so-called compression - semantic compression of the text. Structuring and compression of individual parts of the text are easily implemented on specially compiled or selected educational texts, but it is most difficult on artistic ones. It should be borne in mind that regional studies texts containing historical and cultural information are also more difficult to process in this way, since they are meaningful in almost every sentence.

Texts containing regional and Russian studies-related realities for students serve two roles in the learning process. On the one hand, like any text used in class, they serve to practice verbal skills and abilities. On the other hand, they are designed for immediate assimilation of the linguistic and regional studies content by the reader. Therefore, classes that use texts that implement interdisciplinary connections and convey such information require special preliminary preparation from the teacher. For example, in the specific context of implementing a communicative focus in teaching Russian to Azerbaijani students, we recommend exploiting the close connections between subjects such as language, history, and literature. At the same time, recognizing that a Russian language course cannot completely replace either history or literature, we suggest that when selecting texts, we focus on those stages of Russian history that had a pivotal impact on Russia. Regarding interdisciplinary connections with the literature course, we primarily suggest selecting texts that are somehow related to these epochal stages in Russian history. Finally, as visual aids for each lesson in which one of the selected texts is presented, we recommend supplementing the analysis of lexical and grammatical material with a specific painting by a particular Russian artist or a film (or a fragment) based on the topic of the recommended reading.

In addition to the above, with the setting of different tasks, these can be such ancient films as “Peter the Great”, “Hero of our time”, “The lonely Sail is white”, “My dear man”, “Ivan Vasilyevich is changing his profession”. Due to its popularity and wide distribution among Azerbaijani youth in general, the vocabulary in these films is easily perceived and remembered. However, the list of Russian films can be supplemented with some modern ones with a similar historical theme.

When working at the Faculty of Pedagogy and Philology, it is also necessary to keep in mind the professional orientation of the selection of didactic material. A future language teacher should not only explain himself in a foreign language, but also be able to communicate in it. An exchange of remarks, say, at home or with a casual acquaintance, is not at all identical to the systematic and systematic conduct of a lecture or seminar in a university setting.

Most Azerbaijani methodologists agree that a university graduate in the republic should ideally clearly distinguish some lexical figures from others. For example, to have a clear understanding of synonyms, antonyms, paronyms, homonyms, etc. He must know all the parts of speech, rules and regulations related to case endings. Moreover, we believe that the terminological vocabulary should be introduced gradually, in accordance with the presentation of grammatical material and in full compliance with the requirements of the latest Russian language program published in Azerbaijan in 2020.

Once all sections of Russian linguistics have been studied, it's appropriate to move on to reinforcing them through Russian literature. Moreover, students should pay particular attention to the most striking and revealing moments in works that utilize a linguistic and cultural paradigm. For example, in L. Kassil's novella

“Conduit and Shvambrania”, the teacher draws attention to the episode where the girls’ and boys’ gymnasi-ums merge.

It should be noted that this novel is quite large in volume, complex in structure and vocabulary, and therefore it is probably not advisable to recommend it entirely for reading to Azerbaijani students who do not speak Russian well enough. Although from a psychological and didactic point of view, this story, which tells about the irrepressible youthful fantasy, would be interesting for organizing a discussion on a pedagogical topic. However, we have selected only a part of one of the chapters: “A delicate mission”.

When we talk about linguistic and foreign studies on the history of Russia, we must certainly keep in mind the following: the history of any nation is viewed in the atmosphere of a certain accumulated experience of its social existence. Through historical examples, people are brought up to respect eternal, enduring human values such as freedom, equality, justice, peace, goodness, beauty, etc. By studying the history and culture of the Russian people more deeply over several centuries, students from Azerbaijan will be able to once again verify their authenticity in reality. It is also impossible not to take into account the fact that history is one of the most important forms of self-awareness. The experience of history is used by opposing political forces, and therefore, when interpreting certain events, there is a struggle of different ideas and opinions. Each stage of history is associated with a certain stage in man’s comprehension of the world around him. Firstly, the linguistic and foreign studies material reflecting these realities of people’s daily social life is an additional incentive for

Azerbaijani students to learn Russian. Secondly, it expands the horizons of knowledge about Russia to a certain extent, starting in stages from the antiquity of the Renaissance and ending with the most important modern historical events in people’s lives.

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